

The Role of Situational Leadership and Commitment to Employee Work Satisfaction

Bob Foster

Abstract:

This research was carried out in one of the local government agencies in West Bandung Regency. The study was conducted for 6 (months). The population in the study are employees with a sample of respondents as many as 50 employees. The research method used is descriptive and verification methods. Based on the results of the study, Situational Leadership is in a pretty good category, Commitment in the category is quite good, Job Satisfaction is in a pretty good category and Employee Performance in the Public Government is in a pretty good category. Based on data processing, there is evidence that Situational Leadership and Employee Commitment have a significant effect on job satisfaction. This indicates that the existence of effective situational leadership and high commitment will give satisfaction to the employees. The practical application of this research is to improve the situational leadership and Commitment, providing the opportunities for the subordinates to conduct self-development is essential and giving the understanding by the leader.

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About Author

Bob Foster, Universitas Informatika Dan Bisnis Indonesia, Bandung, 40614, Indonesia.

Introduction

Human Resources is one of the targets of Bureaucratic reform, in addition to the institutional arrangements and organizational management. Human Resources is the driving force of an agency's work unit which is very instrumental in increasing the productivity or performance of an agency's work unit as a whole. The organization as an open system is in an environment. Changes that occur in the organizational environment require attention from managers because it can have a major impact on organizational development. Organizational activities will change the environment, and vice versa, the environment will encourage change in the organization, as well as its influence with the organizational climate created in the interaction between personnel involved in it. The organization considers the importance of developing human resources because at this time Employees are assets that are very important in achieving organizational goals. As time and technology develops, there is a shift in employee perspectives. The point of view which states that humans as a factor of production has gradually shifted and placed humans as assets. This shift in perspective puts employees higher in value when compared to other production tools. To produce quality human resources (HR), individuals who are highly dedicated, and professionals who are able to make meaningful contributions to the organizations that protect them are needed. In carrying out the main duties, responsibilities, authority in the field of activities, HR from the boss level to the lower level employees, need supporting factors including organizational climate and maturity to improve performance. The nature of human resource management is an effort to integrate personnel needs with organizational goals, meaning an increase in the contribution that can be given by workers in the organization towards the achievement of goals. Government organizations certainly cannot be separated from this HR factor, so that it becomes one of the focuses in bureaucratic reform, so that the results can be truly felt by the community. It is important for an organization or institution to pay attention to the quality of human resources and a healthy organizational climate to support the performance process, so that in many organizations evaluating individual performance, organizational performance evaluation or research on organizational culture, organizational climate, work productivity, employee work motivation in the hope of recommendations obtained can provide strategic proposals for improving employee performance. To improve the performance of employees the role of a leader is very important. (Yukl, 2008) In addition to the company providing formal training, non-formal education is also important to be carried out, among others by the leadership of the company as the development of Human Resources (HR). Thus, each organization needs to develop human resources through improving performance so that employees have the ability, skills and positive attitudes so that they are able to carry out their duties well. The existing leadership has not been implemented properly. (Larsson and Vinberg, 2010) These allegations are supported by data on guidance and guidance schedules that are carried out intensively and not optimally. When viewed from the guidance and supervision schedule, it is seen that the leader does not carry out his duties on schedule, so the progress of the Employee's performance is not expected to improve better. Good leadership in an organization is supported by a good organizational culture. Leaders are part of organizational culture, but a leader also has the possibility to act as an agent of change in culture (Yukl, 2011).

From the initial observation, the condition of employee commitment is not ideal, this is seen from the low commitment of employees to the organization. The above conditions also lead to various other activities such as many decision-making processes at each level of leadership that are less rapid, due to the delay in data and information provided by employees, so that in

carrying out the main tasks there are still many mistakes and not in accordance with the established work procedures, This is due to the lack of commitment that is available to each employee. In addition to coaching and creating employees' commitment intensively, leaders must also pay attention to the needs of their subordinates so that job satisfaction is realized in the employees, which in turn will produce the expected performance and in accordance with the goals of the organization. This shows that job satisfaction has been felt, then productivity will increase when followed by the provision of fair rewards and in accordance with the work and needs, with the provision of rewards it is expected that employees can improve their performance. Basically, job satisfaction is an individual thing. Each individual will have a different level of satisfaction in accordance with the value system that applies to him. Job satisfaction also shows the suitability between one's expectations for something and what they really receive, so it can be said that job satisfaction is different for each individual. This is because each individual has differences in the values he adheres to, attitudes, behaviors in doing work. Based on the background and phenomenon above, it is necessary to conduct research on how much influence the situational leadership and commitment to employee job satisfaction have. So that can be obtained an overview of the influence of situational leadership and commitment to employee satisfaction.

Literature Review

An organizational leader must have a commitment that can then influence his subordinates to create employee commitment to carry out the mission and vision of the organization. It is also how a leader can lift subordinate needs from lower levels to a higher level and how that leadership successfully motivates subordinates to defeat their personal interests for the sake of a larger team, organization or group (Yukl, 2011). Leadership theory (Bryman, 2011) assumes that leadership of a leader can be systematically developed and improved. For a leader in dealing with a situation that demands leadership applications can go through several processes such as: understanding the leadership style, diagnosing a situation, applying leadership that is relevant to the demands of the situation or by changing the situation to suit his leadership style. (Yammarino, 2013) This will encourage the emergence of good faith or commitment of members to their organizations. According to social cognitive theory (Bandura, 1977; Gibson, 2004) states that employees are motivated to maintain and strengthen self-esteem and self-esteem. The aspect of self-concept emphasized personal commitment to leaders and missions; willingness to sacrifice for a common mission; and meaning in their work and life. Furthermore, according to Mowday, Porter and Steers (2013) organizational commitment is a condition in which employees are very interested in the goals, values and goals of the organization. While leadership is a pattern of behavior designed to integrate organizational goals with individual goals to achieve certain goals. (Shin, et al, 2011). Leadership theory (Bryman, 2011) assumes that leadership of a leader can be systematically developed and improved. For a leader in dealing with a situation that requires application of leadership style can go through several processes such as: understanding the leadership style, diagnosing a situation, applying leadership styles that are relevant to the demands of the situation or by changing the situation to suit his leadership style. This will encourage the emergence of good faith or commitment of members to their organizations.

Effect of Situational Leadership on Job Satisfaction

A successful leader is a leader who is able to apply his influence to suit a particular situation. A leader needs to consider each situation in order to understand which style is more

appropriate. So what is done by superiors has an influence on subordinates, which can generate enthusiasm and excitement for the work so that the goals of the organization can be achieved in accordance with what has been set. Leadership according to Blanchard and Hersey (1996) states that leadership is a pattern of behavior when someone tries to influence others and they accept it. Blanchard categorizes situational leadership that is directing, training, supporting and delegating which if this is carried out well by the leader, there will be a commitment to each employee / subordinate. Then the subordinates are given reward and punishment attention such as a decent salary, bonuses and promotion, so that each employee will experience satisfaction in carrying out their work so that if the three things materialize then performance will be as expected. Leadership behavior is the degree to which a leader will set and compose his role and the role of his subordinates in an effort to achieve goals. Leaders are oriented to work where the behavior of their leaders in the completion of their duties provides tasks, regulates the implementation, supervises and evaluates the performance of subordinates as a result of the execution of tasks. (Yukl and Mahsud, 2010) While effective leadership behavior is leadership behavior that can mobilize subordinates to achieve common goals that are in accordance with the wishes of the leader without neglecting subordinate satisfaction (McCleskey, 2014). Employee job satisfaction will arise when a leader is able to motivate, direct, guide, have a sense of attention, create a conducive work environment so that from the work of subordinates, leaders are able to provide rewards. Then it can be said that a good leadership style and in accordance with the needs of the organization will create job satisfaction.

Effect of Commitment to Job Satisfaction

Commitment is as a level of trust and acceptance of the workforce towards the goals of the organization and has a desire to remain in the organization where the determining factor is job satisfaction, because if the employee is satisfied the employee will be more committed to the organization or in other words a person is not satisfied with his work or lack of commitment to the organization will be seen withdrawing from the organization either through absence or in and out of the office. Thus, employees who have a strong commitment will always be in the organization, and potentially will improve their performance. Expert opinion that without a strong commitment from employees, the efforts of an organization to present a quality service will fail and employees who are committed to the values of the organization will have the will to work seriously to achieve the goals of the organization (Biswas and Bhatnagar, 2013). An employee will feel satisfied with the results of his work because he has been serious in carrying out his obligations, this is due to a high commitment as part of the organization. Likewise the commitment will grow in the employee because in the company he has felt job satisfaction, job satisfaction is related to wages / salaries, opportunities for promotion, and others.

Effect of Situational Leadership and Commitment to Job Satisfaction

Situational leadership is a way of leadership to influence other people or subordinates in such a way that the person wants to do the will of the leader to achieve organizational goals even though personally it may not be liked to convey to the situation at hand. According to Yukl and Mahsud (2010) leadership has a strong positive effect on performance, also has a significant effect on organizational learning. This finding gives an indication that a leader's situational leadership is very influential on the performance of his subordinates, in addition to getting a good performance it is also necessary to provide learning to his subordinates. Leadership theory (Bryman, 2011) assumes that leadership of a leader can be systematically

developed and improved. For a leader in dealing with a situation that demands the application of leadership styles can go through several processes such as: understanding his leadership, diagnosing a situation, applying leadership styles that are relevant to the demands of the situation or by changing the situation to suit his leadership style. This will encourage the emergence of good faith or commitment of members to their organizations. Strong commitment from employees in the organization to deliver a quality service if employees are committed to the values of the organization and have the willingness to work seriously (Azeem, 2010; Biswas and Bhatnagar, 2013; Rafiq Awan and Mahmood, 2010; Slack, Orife and Anderson, 2010). Employee job satisfaction will arise when a leader is able to motivate, direct, guide, have a sense of attention, create a conducive work environment so that from the work of subordinates, leaders are able to provide rewards. (Bass, 2008) So it can be said that a good leadership style and in accordance with the needs of the organization will create job satisfaction (Larsson and Vinberg, 2010).

Methods

This research was carried out in one of the intensities of the government in West Bandung Regency. This research was conducted for four months in 2017. The population is an area of generalization consisting of objects or subjects that have certain qualities and characteristics set by researchers to be studied and then drawn conclusions. The population in this study were employees of the Department of Transportation, Communication and Information of West Bandung Regency. The sample in this study was taken from the overall population of 50 people. In getting a good result on a problem so that the desired goals and benefits can be achieved, then in the implementation it requires accurate data in accordance with the need to be used as material for procuring assessment. Accurate data is data that meets the requirements of validity and data that meets its reliability. To obtain and obtain accurate data as is commonly used and valid in the world of science, it is carried out and obtained through the correct research method and carried out according to the level of needs. Based on the description related to the research method above it can be concluded that the research method is a method used by researchers to obtain or collect valid data with specific purposes and uses. The research method used in this research is descriptive analysis method, because this study in addition to wanting to get an overview of leadership style, commitment, job satisfaction and employee performance, also wants to get an overview of the relationship pattern and the influence of the specified research variables. The research variables set are as follows; situational leadership functions as an independent variable which is then given a notation (X1); commitment functions as an independent variable which is then given a notation (X2) and job satisfaction as a dependent variable which is then given a notation (Y). The steps that will be taken to process the data obtained from the questionnaire that has been filled in by the respondent are as follows: 1) Processing answers from questionnaires that have been filled by respondents by calculating the frequency and percentage; 2) Giving weighting to each respondent's answer will be assessed on an ordinal scale. The analysis technique used is descriptive analysis technique. Descriptive analysis technique is used to describe the variables of Leadership Style (X1), Commitment (X2), Job Satisfaction (Y) by using multiple regression analysis.

Data Analysis

From the interpretation criteria the results of the frequency data processing of each variable can be determined as follows:

Table 1 Score

Variables	Mean
Situational Leadership	3,39
Commitment	3,28
Job Satisfaction	3,34

Based on the table above, it can be seen that the variables of Situational Leadership, Commitment, and Job Satisfaction of employees are categorized as good enough. The table above shows the average score of the Commitment variable is lower than the Leadership variable, meaning that in actual conditions the Situational Leadership variable contributes to or greater influence on Job Satisfaction compared to the Commitment variable.

Table 2 Correlation Analysis

		X1	X2
X1	Pearson Correlation	1	0,286*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0,016
	N	71	71
X2	Pearson Correlation	0,286*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0,016	
	N	71	71

From the table above it can be concluded, that:

The relationship between the Situational Leadership variable (X1) and Commitment (X2) is obtained by a value of 0.286, so that if it is consented with the interpretation table of r (correlation) values, it has a weak but unidirectional relationship level because its value is positive. Correlation of X1 and X2 is significant because the significance number (0.00) is smaller than 0.05.

Table 3 R² Score

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.775 ^a	.601	.589	4.037060

From the data above, the coefficient is terminated (total influence) Situational Leadership (X1), Commitment (X2) to job satisfaction (Y) seen from R Square of 0.601. While the rest of 0.399 is the epsilon variable, which is a variable that affects job satisfaction but was not examined in this study.

Table 4 Result of regressions

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-4.247	5.596		-.759	.450
	X1	.752	.095	.634	7.929	.000
	X2	.328	.087	.300	3.755	.000

The table above is a data processing path coefficient table showing that the value of the Situational Leadership coefficient (X1) is 0.752 and the Commitment (X2) path coefficient value is 0.328. Based on the table above, it can be seen that the situational leadership and commitment variable has a direct influence on job satisfaction. And the total effect of situational leadership and commitment on job satisfaction is 60.1%.

Discussion

Based on the respondents' answers regarding Situational Leadership, the employees are categorized as good with 3.39. The Situational Leadership has a higher average compared with the Commitment variable. However, among 15 statements, item number 5 is the lowest value, the leader always involves subordinates in problem-solving with an average value of 2.67. It means that the respondents do not realize that the leader is not fully involved the employee in solving the problem. Besides, the statement number 6, the Leader gives the opportunity to the subordinates to carry out self-development with a value of 2.80, which means that the leader does not give the opportunity to the employees to develop themselves. From the variable dimensions of situational leadership, it can be seen that the dimension supports the lowest score, with a score of 3.08. This condition illustrates that the leader cannot provide the optimal support regarding encouraging the employees to improve their abilities, giving attention to employees' performance and recognition of the achievements that have been achieved by the employees. According to Blanchard and Hersey (1996), leadership is a pattern of behavior when someone tries to influence the others, and they accept it. Blanchard categorizes situational leadership that consists of directing, training, supporting and delegating. When the leader carries out those elements effectively, the employee/subordinate will commit. Furthermore, the subordinates are given reward and punishment such as a decent salary, bonuses, and promotion. Therefore, each employee will be satisfied in carrying out their work. If the three aspects are materialized, then performance will be as expected. Based on the respondent's answer, Commitment is categorized as good with 3.28. This finding shows a positive response from the respondents regarding the Commission. However, based on the explanation of the respondent's item number 9, the respondents gave a minimum answer with a score of 2.57. The statement is 'I sincerely carried out the task in the organization where I worked' which meant that the employees' commitment in carrying out the task is not based on the sincerity. Item number 10 states that 'I am willing to accept sanctions if it violates the rules set by the organization' with 2.71 which means that employees do not become aware of their mistakes. The results of the dimensions of the commitment variable's score indicate that the dimensions of belief and acceptance of the values and goals of the organization have a score with the lowest value of 3.07. This situation illustrates that employees' commitment to always be obedient to the organization, maintain the good name of the organization and strive to realize organizational goals is not yet optimal. According to social cognitive theory (Bandura, 1977; Gibson, 2004), the employees are motivated to maintain and strengthen the self-esteem. The aspect of self-concept emphasized personal commitment to leaders and missions; willingness to sacrifice for a joint mission; and meaning in their work and life. This aspect will encourage the emergence of members' faith or commitment to their organizations (Aydogdu and Asikgil, 2011). Based on the respondents' answers, the job satisfaction is categorized as good with 3.34. This result means that employees are satisfied enough. Of the 18 statement items, there is a statement with low value. It is the item number 6 with a statement: 'I always want protection from the organization for the work I do.' The value is 2.77 which means that the employee still needs protection from the working place. Statement number 8 is, 'I am satisfied

with the incentive money.' The value is 2.65 which means the employees are not satisfied with the incentive money. In other words, the incentive that has been implemented is not optimal. Furthermore, at the dimensions of the variable job satisfaction, the dimension of the work itself has the lowest score with 3.10. This result shows that a sense of pride, responsibility and a feeling of appreciation for the successful work by the employee is not optimal. Employee job satisfaction depends on the fulfillment of employees' needs. Employees are satisfied when they get what they need. The greater the fulfillment of employee's needs, the more satisfied the employee is. Likewise, if the employee's needs are not fulfilled, the employee will be dissatisfied. Employee job satisfaction is in a proper category. As shown by several indicators such as: happy with the job, understand the job description, receive enough incentives, promotion opportunity, the award for achievement and get some help from colleagues and superiors. The description of job satisfaction above is also consistent with the theory proposed in this study, namely the measurement of job satisfaction by Luthans, et al, (2015) proposes five dimensions that are formulated and used to measure job satisfaction, namely: Work itself, Salary, Promotional opportunities, Supervision, and co-workers. Employee job satisfaction will arise when a leader can motivate, direct, guide, have a sense of attention, create a conducive work environment so that from the work of subordinates, leaders can provide rewards. The situational leadership variable has a direct influence of 40.2%. The indirect influence through its relationship with commitment is 5.4%, and the total effect is 45.6%. The influence of situational leadership gives the most significant contribution compared to commitment. This finding shows that the role of leaders in providing employee satisfaction is dominant. A successful leader is a leader who can influence the others to suit a particular situation. A leader needs to consider each situation in order to understand the most appropriate style. Therefore, what is done by superiors influences subordinates, which can generate enthusiasm and excitement for the work? Furthermore, the organization can achieve the goals. The results of this study support by Yukl and Mahsud (2010) which stated that leadership influences the employees' job satisfaction. Effective leadership has an impact on employees' job satisfaction. Job satisfaction affects a person's presence in the world of work. (Mosadeghrad and Ferdosi, 2013) Furthermore, it also affects the willingness to work. Employee desires or motivation to work are usually aimed at supporting activities that lead to goals. (Zulfikar, 2016)

The results show that commitment has a direct influence of 9% and indirect influence through its relationship with leadership is 5.4%. The total effect is 14.4%. The contribution of commitment to job satisfaction is still weak. If linked to the situational leadership variable, the contribution of commitment will increase. In reality, commitment gives a modest contribution, and the employees own it. However, when compared with leadership, there will be a difference where the leadership is powerful. The strong direction from the leadership in helping troubled employees and giving encouragement to achieve the best performance indicate the power of leadership, to provide employee satisfaction in work. The results of the research are in line with the statement of Mowday, et al, (2013) that without a firm commitment from employees, it leads to failed service. Moreover, employees who are committed to the values of the organization have the will to work earnestly to achieve the organizational goals. The simultaneous influence of situational leadership and commitment to job satisfaction is 60.1%. Situational leadership has the most dominant influence on job satisfaction. The situational leadership of employees at the respondent's answer is in a suitable category. Employees are satisfied with their work, but there are many unexamined variables which affect job satisfaction. Based on the phenomenon in the field, there are many

factors that affect job satisfaction but are not examined in this study as employees are not comfortable with boss leadership, work environment conditions are not conducive, employee work performance needs to be improved, employee work ethic needs to be improved, training for employees needs to be improved, employee career development is unclear, work infrastructure facilities are not optimal, short and long-term work programs have not achieved the target, the implementation of cross-program or sector work programs for the community has not been well coordinated so that it becomes a whole and continuous program and division of tasks/jobs employee work description needs to be reviewed again.

Conclusion and Recommendation

The exposure of respondents is in the good category. However, there are some weak aspects it can be seen at the dimension supports the lowest score regarding situational leadership. The employee commitment is categorized as adequate. However, there are some weak aspects it can be seen at dimensions of belief and acceptance of the values and goals of the organization. The respondent's exposure regarding employee job satisfaction is in a pretty good category. However, there are some weak aspects it can be seen at the dimensions of the variable job satisfaction, the dimension of the work itself has the lowest score. In the other hands, there are some weak aspects of situational leadership and commitment. Partially and simultaneously, they have an effect on employees' job satisfaction. To improve the situational leadership, providing the opportunities for the subordinates to conduct self-development is essential. Therefore, the role and involvement of employees in solving the problems is expected to improve the effective leadership by involving in decision making. To increase the employee commitment, giving the understanding by the leader. The employees want to carry out their duties sincerely and do not violate the rules in the organization. To increase Job Satisfaction, employees need an improvement of a proper and fair incentive system and the role of leaders in providing good understanding such as giving the training of emotional and spiritual quotient.

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